

STORYTELLING ALOUD STRATEGY: EFFECTS ON PUPILS' READING COMPREHENSION SKILL

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Storytelling Aloud Strategy: Effects on Pupils' Reading Comprehension Skill

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Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly impacted education, particularly in the area of reading skills among young learners. This quasi-experimental study investigates interactive Read-Aloud sessions' effectiveness in improving kindergarten pupils' reading comprehension skills (ages 5-6) at Lingating Integrated School, Lingating, Baungon, Bukidnon. The study involved eighty heterogeneous pupils, with forty exposed to the reading-aloud strategy and forty to the conventional non-reading-aloud strategy. Results indicate that the storytelling aloud strategy significantly enhanced kindergarteners' reading comprehension, suggesting its potential as an intervention in early childhood education. While both groups showed similar academic performance, the storytelling group displayed slightly higher grades. Recommendations include incorporating storytelling into the classroom routine, utilizing non-storytelling strategies like games, providing more reading material, and implementing storytelling across various subjects. This research underscores the importance of interactive Read-Aloud sessions in fostering reading skills among kindergarten pupils, emphasizing the need for diverse strategies to enhance learning outcomes in early education settings.

Keywords: *storytelling aloud strategy, reading comprehension skill*

Introduction

Reading is a problem now with our school because of the pandemic we have experienced for the past two years. I observed that most of the learners had problems with reading comprehension. Some of my learners have difficulty identifying letter sounds and letter names in my kindergarten class. Reading is not solely a skill but a combination of many skills and processes in which the readers interact with printed words and texts for content and pleasure.

The primary goals of reading are to enable students to understand the world and themselves, develop appreciation and interests, and find solutions to their personal and group problems.

However, reading is a human skill that requires a whole process to understand it. It is present from infant education until we die, which means it is a process that lasts during all of our lives, and it has a real influence not only in educational settings but also in social and commutative aspects.

Pupils start to add more vocabulary and acquire cultural knowledge from this first stage thanks to reading but also listening to stories or short tales, which means they are continuously working with the basic abilities to learn a new language.

Once they can understand more complex sentences, they are ready to take advantage of their skills. aspects, but the school is meant to be the best support because it is the place where pupils spend most of their time not only physically and surrounded by books but also mentally. The school does result in a perfect place to develop an interest in reading.

However, with the current situation, learners cannot come to read at school. This message is especially important this year, as States will establish a new agenda for education and development to steer the next 15 years, according to Ms. Bokova's statements on the Day. This new approach must put literacy promotion first, she insisted. "Literacy advances sustainable development by empowering individual women and men, advancing everything from better healthcare and food security to reducing poverty and fostering good jobs." Since 2000, the globe has advanced.

According to Ms. Bokova, "but high hurdles remain." The number of out-of-school children and adolescents is on the rise, standing at 124 million worldwide, while about 250 million children of primary school age are failing to master basic literacy skills even in schooling, according to the expert. She also noted that 757 million adults still lack basic literacy skills, with two-thirds of them being women.

Students frequently have trouble decoding words, have weak comprehension abilities, and have limited reading fluency. Despite these initiatives, reading proficiency in the Philippines still falls short of that in other nations in the region. The lack of emphasis on reading in the Philippine educational system may be one factor in this. The majority of schools do not provide pupils enough time to read independently, and many teachers lack the necessary expertise to successfully teach reading.

Reading words that are frequently used in their language, reading non-words using their knowledge of phonics, fluently reading and comprehending a narrative text, responding to comprehension questions about a short story after listening to it, and writing a dictated sentence were all included in the assessment of students' foundational literacy skills using the SRYA tool.

Together, teachers and parents should choose the approach that will benefit each pupil the most, offering ample support to help them advance their reading abilities. One of the easiest and most efficient intervention options for students who struggle with reading is reading aloud. Children can be two and a half years ahead in reading readiness when they attend kindergarten, according to reading

experts, which has a significant impact on a young mind and provides kids a head start on their education. Pauses when reading aloud play an essential role in reading and listening comprehension (Godde et al., 2020).

This research has its benefits to the administrators, teachers, learners, future researchers, and parents; reading to kids helps them understand more. Their understanding increases when they aren't stressed out about things like reading aloud or correctly pronouncing difficult words. Reading aloud improves vocabulary.

Moreover, the researcher did not find any local study conducted like this proposal especially at DepEd Bukidnon Division thus, this study will have to be conducted to find out the effect of reading aloud strategy to the pupils' reading comprehension skill.

In school where the researcher is teaching, the researcher observes that learners have poor comprehension skills. Seeing the critical role of reading skills in terms of the academic performance of the learners, the researcher was motivated to conduct this research.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the storytelling strategy for kindergarten learners and its implications for their academic performance. Specifically, this study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What are the level of pre-test and post-test mean scores in the reading comprehension of the kindergarten learners exposed to the storytelling aloud strategy as well as those exposed to the non-storytelling strategy?
2. Is there a significant difference in the pre-test and post-test mean scores in the reading comprehension of the kindergarten learners exposed to storytelling aloud and non-storytelling strategy?
3. What is the level of academic performance of the kindergarten learners exposed to storytelling aloud and non-storytelling aloud strategy?
4. Is there a significant difference in the academic performance of the kindergarten learners exposed to storytelling aloud and non-storytelling strategy?

Methodology

Research Design

This research utilizes the quasi-experimental design. As defined, a quasi-experimental design aims to establish a cause-and-effect relationship between an independent and dependent variable (Thomas, 2020). It is an experimental design in which assignment of participants to an experimental group or to a control group cannot be made at random for either practical or ethical reasons (American Psychological Association, 2022); this is a research designs that that aim to identify the impact of a particular intervention, program or event (a "treatment") by comparing treated units to control units (Dimewiki, 2022).

This research design is employed in the study because the researcher wants to determine the effect of the Reading Aloud Strategy on kindergarten comprehension skills.

Also, quasi-experimental design simulates experimental circumstances where some participants receive the intervention while others do not on a random basis. the kinder pupils' reading comprehension skills. Participants are assigned without randomization as either part of the experimental and non-experimental group.

Participants

This study examines how well interactive Read-Aloud sessions help kindergarten pupils (ages 5-6) improve their reading comprehension skills. The participants of the study are the kindergarten pupils of Lingating Integrated School, Lingating, Baungon, Bukidnon. Only eighty (80) heterogenous pupils will be part of the study. These pupils are currently enrolled this School year 2022-2023. Forty (40) pupils were exposed to the reading-aloud strategy, and forty (40) were exposed to the conventional non-reading-aloud strategy.

This study utilizes two intact kindergarten classes, and the researcher employed simple random sampling to select the participants. This study is limited to the kinder pupils of Lingating Integrated School, Lingating, Baungon, Bukidnon for the school year 2022-2023. This study has a time frame of 1-year. It began this first semester of the school year 2022-2023. Only the kinder pupils of Lingating Integrated School included in this study have the written approval of their parents. Assent Form and Informed Consent were retrieved from each participant and/or their parents/guardian prior to the conduct of the study. Data were treated with privacy and confidentiality. Completed questionnaires were kept in a secured area to avoid the possible risks of the participants.

Instruments

For the pre-test and post-test questionnaires, the researcher used the standardized DepED reading comprehension survey questionnaire for kindergarten pupils for first and second quarter school year 2022-2023. The said instrument is a 50 items examination made up of different objective types of tests. Furthermore, the items included in the questionnaire are extracted or sourced from the DepED Kinder modules and kindergarten Alternative Delivery Mode Quarter 1 module 1-10 and Quarter 2 module 11-20, first Edition 2020. This Module owned by DepEd and their respective writers and illustrators. The Publisher does not represent nor claim ownership over them.

Published by Department Of Education - Division of El Salvador City School Division Superintendent: Olga C. Alonsabe , CESE .learning manual. The questionnaire is adopted from the kindergarten curriculum provided by the Division office. items were adapted to suit the learner's needs.

Procedure

A letter of request to conduct the study was submitted to the Dean's office of the School of Teacher Education as well as to the Schools Division Superintendent of DepEd of Bukidnon upon the endorsement of the thesis adviser. Then the signed request was presented to the principal/school head of Lingating Integrated School for implementation. Pupils were then oriented on the aims or purpose of the study and how the study would be implemented. Moreover, a clearance was obtained from the Research Ethics Board and carried out in a morally and ethically responsible way and made sure that the research produces useful outcomes.

Pretest was administered to all the participants to obtain baseline data prior to the conduct or implementation of the strategy. During the implementation of the study, the pupils in the experimental group were exposed to the reading-aloud strategy for a duration of three months. The study focused on the concepts of Kinder English subject specifically on their lessons on reading comprehension. On the other hand, the pupils in the control group were exposed to the usual non-reading-aloud strategy. After which, participants were tasked to answer posttest questions which is a similar evaluation measure previously distributed prior to intervention implementation.

Furthermore, the pre-test and post-test score were tallied using the MS Excel and forwarded to the statistician for computations of the data following the research problems. The researcher recorded the Data total score divided by the number of items in the questionnaire and its result was given a description value.

Description Value if the child got the score of 60-79 % he or she belongs to the beginning and when the child got the score 80- 89 % he or she belongs to the Developing and then when the child got the score of 90-100, he or she is consistent. The result of the scoring is Identified whether that learners belong to the Beginning, Developing and Consistent.

Data Analysis

To answer problems 1 and 2, the researcher used the descriptive mean and standard deviation. For problem 3, to determine the effect of the intervention on the pupils' reading comprehension skills, ANCOVA or Analysis of Covariance were used and for the problem 4 and 5 are T-test.

The basic process for ANCOVA (1) Perform separate linear regressions on the response as a function of the covariate for each of the treatment groups and determine that at least one of those lines has a Fig. 9 (A, B) Approximate curve shapes covered in this paper by the common base method Ganger et al. BMC Bioinformatics (2020) 21:423 Page 21 of 27 slope statistically different from zero. (If all slopes are zero, then the covariate may be ignored, and ordinary ANOVA used instead.) (2) Verify homogeneity of slopes for the lines. Although it is unlikely that the regression step produced lines with identical slopes, it is possible that the data fit a model with an enforced common slope.

Assessing the significance of the interaction term between the treatment and covariate, in this case diet*temperature, is necessary to determine the homogeneity of slopes. You will usually perform some type of fit for a general linear model, which accepts a response, a treatment, and a covariate, depending on the software you use (perhaps under an ANOVA menu). You can often enter the interaction term in the "model" option. A p-value for the interaction should be included in the output. The null hypothesis that the slopes are the same is tested by the p-value for this interaction. If the p-value is higher than 0.05, the null hypothesis is not rejected, and you may infer that the slopes are homogeneous.

The slopes of the lines are probably different if the p-value is less than 0.05, indicating that there is a significant interaction between the treatment and covariate. ANCOVA is not suited in this situation. (3) Rerun the general linear model routine in cases where slopes are homogeneous in order to recalculate the regression lines with a new imposed common slope. This should be done without the interaction term. For pairwise comparisons of treatments, most software programs should also provide choices for "contrasts" or "comparisons" that will produce confidence intervals. We shall refrain from imposing our preference for one of the several contrast kinds (Fisher, Tukey, Sidak, or Bonferonni).

Assessing the significance of the interaction term between the treatment and covariate, in this case diet*temperature is necessary to determine the homogeneity of slopes. Researchers usually perform some type of fit for a general linear model, which accepts a response, a treatment, and a covariate, depending on the software you use (perhaps under an ANOVA menu). You can often enter the interaction term in the "model" option. A p-value for the interaction should be included in the output. The null hypothesis showing that the slopes are the same is tested by the p-value for this interaction. If the p-value is higher than 0.05, the null hypothesis is not rejected, and you may infer that the slopes are homogeneous.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the quantitative data obtained about the posited problem of the study. The pertinent data were analyzed, interpreted, and presented in Tables following the sequence of the research problem.

Problem 1. What are the level of Pre-test and post-test mean score in the reading comprehension of the kindergarten learners exposed to the storytelling aloud strategy.

Table 1. *Level of Pre-test and post-test mean score in the reading comprehension of the kindergarten learners exposed to storytelling aloud strategy*

Type of Performance	N	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Pre-test	40	27.50	11.1	Satisfactory
Post-test	40	43.82	5.59	Outstanding

Legend: 41-50, Outstanding; 31-40, Very Satisfactory; 21-30, Satisfactory; 11-20, Poor; 10-Below, Needs Improvement

Table 1 presents the Level of Reading Comprehension of Kindergarten Learners when Exposed to the Storytelling Aloud Strategy in terms of Pre-Test and Post-Test. As shown in the Table, the pre-test performance of the participants has a mean score of 27.50 interpreted as satisfactory while post-test performance is higher with a mean of 43.82 interpreted as outstanding. Based on these mean scores, it can be interpreted that the kindergarteners exposed to this Storytelling Aloud Strategy have better performance during their post-test. Reading aloud strategy can be used every day. Teachers may increase Reading Achievement by using studies on reading motivation and engagement. They can start with the components of SMILE (S = sharing; M = me; I = importance; L = liking; E = engagement) to encourage motivation in the classroom. Furthermore, the increase of kindergarteners' performance from their pre-test to post-test could be attributed to the storytelling aloud strategy used which students found effective.

Some learners might believe that textbooks are dull and difficult to understand. Many learners' texts lack sufficient supplemental explanation to draw the dots between disparate pieces of information, which may make comprehension more challenging. Students' sense of failure increases if they can't understand the text they're reading, and the textbook is the foundation of the curriculum. Pupils should have access to supplementary materials, such as a set of readings on the same subject that range from very simple to very complex, or supplemental trade materials, to provide resources on various content topics and aid in the development of deeper background knowledge pertinent to course material.

According to domain-general conceptualizations of academic engagement (e.g., Reeve, 2012), reading engagement refers to a person's actual involvement in reading as manifested in behavior, affect, or cognition (Guthrie, Wigfield, & You, 2012). Reading motivation captures people's thoughts and feelings. As an illustration, behavioral engagement can be seen in a child's sustained focus while reading, affective engagement can be seen in a child's body language and facial expressions when discussing a book, and cognitive engagement can be seen in a child's thoughtful answers to teacher questions (Lutz et al., 2006; Taboada Barber, Gallagher, et al., 2015).

This finding supports the claim of (Layne, 2015) that Read-aloud gives students positive interactions with books, their peers, and their teachers, as well as chances for deeper comprehension, interpretations, enjoyment, and higher-level thinking. Different read-aloud exercises can improve and deepen students' comprehension, vocabulary, and understandings while providing a forum for other viewpoints (Fall, 2018).

Through the read-aloud, voice-enabled a cultural event to advance a deeper comprehension of time, place, people, and culture. Students in this setting gain confidence through language learning and self-expression as they make sense of the dialogic utterances (Lennox, 2013).

The method also helped them understand the read-aloud better. Active involvement with complicated literature can help students grasp a text better in addition to giving in-depth vocabulary guidance before, during, and after read aloud. Active engagement can take the form of exercises like teachers and students debating prior knowledge of a subject before reading the text, teachers assisting students in making connections to other read-aloud or to personal experiences, and teachers posing inferential questions that can result in fruitful discussions about the text (Authors, 2016; Collins, 2016; Giroir et al., 2015; Parsons). et al., 2016).

In conclusion, well planned teacher-student exchanges before, during, and after reading the text seem to be crucial for enhancing students' comprehension of what they hear and increasing their competence and confidence in formulating their own thoughts about the book's content. subsequently communicate to others (Author et al., 2013; Beck & McKeown, 2007)

Problem 2. What is the level of Pre-test and post-test mean scores in the reading comprehension of the kindergarten learners exposed to the non-storytelling aloud strategy?

Table 2 presents the Level of Pre-test and post-test mean scores in the reading comprehension of the kindergarten learners exposed to non-storytelling aloud strategy. As shown in the Table, the pre-test performance of the students has a mean score of 34.97 interpreted as very satisfactory while post-test performance is slightly higher with a mean of 36.75 interpreted as very satisfactory.

Based on these mean scores, it can be interpreted that the kindergarteners exposed to this Non-Storytelling Aloud Strategy have almost similar performance from pre-test to post-test though there was a little increase of mean score during the post-test.

Table 2. *Level of Pre-test and post-test mean score in the reading comprehension of the kindergarten learners exposed to non-storytelling aloud strategy*

Type of Performance	N	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Pre-test	40	34.97	8.80	Very Satisfactory
Post-test	40	36.75	6.48	Very Satisfactory

Legend: 41-50, Outstanding; 31-40, Very Satisfactory; 21-30, Satisfactory; 11-20, Poor; 10-Below, Needs Improvement

Furthermore, the little increase of mean score during the post-test would mean that the non-storytelling aloud strategy used is not an effective strategy for kindergarteners. Primary caregivers are frequently urged to read to their children from an early age since it is crucial for language development.

On the other hand, little is known about what age reading should begin. 104 kids had their language abilities tested just before starting school. We asked the parents how old their kids were when they first started reading to them and how frequently they had done so. Nearly half of the study's participants were first read to when they were just 6 months old. Children's linguistic and cognitive abilities, the frequency with which they were read to as preschoolers, and the age at which they were first read to all had a strong correlation with the age at which they were first read to.

The results suggest that reading to very young children does, in fact, make a significant contribution to a positive family literacy environment and promote children's language development. This finding supports that claim of (Isidro & Teichert, 2021; Kalimullina et al., 2021; Kim et al., 2021). All of this causes reading quality to decline, which in turn lowers the literacy level of the younger generation in general and the reader. It is significant that reading has become a crucial determinant of one's success or failure in a variety of sectors of life (Chudinova, 2012; Saenko et al., 2020; Poghosyan, 2018).

The nature and methods of working with printed and electronic texts, as well as reader preferences, are changing at the same time as a new reading model is being accepted. These models include Borodina and Borodin's "The Role of Reading for Obtaining Information in the World of Computers," Vishniakova's "Dynamic reading methodology," and "Acmeological reading technology (Borodina, 2017). The issue of developing a proficient reader is also being discussed (Smetannikova, 2007; Tikhomirova, 2004; Koshkarov, 2020; Volkova, et al., 2020; Akhmadeev & Bykanova, 2021), and the development of efficient reading strategies during the literary education process (Svirina, 2012). However, in analyzing the issue in all of this research, the focus is on the socio-psychological and educational interpretation of the reading phenomena.

Problem 3. Is there a significant difference in the pre-test and post-test mean score in the reading comprehension of kindergarten learners exposed to storytelling aloud and non-storytelling aloud strategies?

Table 3. *The significant difference in the pre-test and posttest mean score in the reading comprehension of kindergarten learners exposed to storytelling aloud and non-storytelling aloud strategy*

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	2301.08(a)	2	1150.54	56.74	.000	.596
Intercept	5547.77	1	5547.77	273.60	.000	.780
Pretest	1299.97	1	1299.97	64.11	.000	.454
Group	1792.37	1	1792.37	88.39	.000	.534
Error	1561.30	77	20.277			
Total	133709.00	80				
Corrected Total	3862.388	79				

Estimated Marginal Means of Non-Story Telling Aloud Mean = 35.22
Estimated Marginal Means of Story Telling Aloud Mean = 45.34

Table 3 presents significant difference in the pre-test and posttest mean score in the reading comprehension of kindergarten learners exposed to storytelling aloud and non-storytelling aloud strategy.

There was a significant difference in the mean post-test performance [$F(1,77) = 88.39, p = 0.000$] between the students exposed to storytelling aloud and non-storytelling aloud strategies while adjusting for pre-test. The partial Eta Squared value of .534, implied a moderate effect (0.2 – small effect, 0.5 – moderate effect, 0.8 – large effect) of the story telling aloud strategy to the kindergarteners' post-test scores in Reading Comprehension.

Furthermore, when the effect of pre-test is statistically removed, students exposed to storytelling aloud gained the most performance in post-test for reading comprehension as indicated in the estimated marginal means of 45.34. This finding revealed that story telling aloud strategy is an effective intervention in improving the kindergarteners' reading comprehension. One of the easiest and most efficient intervention options for students who struggle with reading is reading aloud. When a pupil hears someone else read, they are better able to comprehend the text and retain the knowledge.

Additionally, a student's fluency and pronunciation can be enhanced by reading aloud. Reading aloud can be used in a variety of settings, including the school and the home. Students reading aloud to one another is one strategy that can improve their oral communication abilities. As an alternative, parents can foster a love of reading in their children and aid in vocabulary growth by reading aloud to them each night before bed.

This finding supports the claims of Chumworatayee et al. (2016) employed to promote metacognitive awareness of reading techniques in L2 readers. It has 30 items and is intended to assess readers' use of three different types of reading strategies: global, problem-solving, and support. conclusions from the prior research show similarities and variations, frequency patterns, and connections between the usage of strategies and various reading or English proficiency levels.

According to research, reading aloud to kids has many positive effects on their language and reading development, and these effects grow the more actively the kids participate in the read-out experience. When reading aloud to children, you can boost their interest by building up their anticipation for the story, offering predictions about what will happen next, and other similar activities. establishing relationships with the characters and using dialogic reading techniques.

This document offers specific suggestions for involving young children. Given that a child's time in a classroom is limited, every activity that would regularly take up that time must be regarded as academically worthwhile. Reading aloud in class 23 has gained popularity as a crucial academic activity ever since the publication of *Becoming a Nation of Readers* (Anderson, Hiebert, Scott & Wilkinson, 2015) and many see it as one of the methods that is effective in cultivating lifelong readers (International Literacy Association [ILA], 2018).

Reading aloud to youngsters has been shown to have short-term benefits for their language development through the primary grades and some beneficial long-term impacts on older kids (Klein & Kogan, 2013). Studies show that read-aloud have educational benefits (ILA, 2018) claim there are specific components of reading aloud that have a good impact on children's language and reading abilities (ILA, 2018). The frequency of reading aloud, the conversation that takes place while reading, and the degree of the kids' engagement during the reading experience seem to be favorable aspects affecting the language of children (Keller, 2012; Klein & Kogan, 2013; Klosterman et al., 2011; Worthy, Chamberlain, Peterson, Sharp & Shih, 2012).

Problem 4. What is the level of academic performance of the kindergarten learners exposed to storytelling aloud and non-storytelling aloud strategy?

Table 4. *Level of academic performance of the kindergarten learners exposed to storytelling aloud and non-storytelling aloud strategy*

<i>Group</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Kindergarteners' Exposed to Story Telling Aloud Strategy	40	85.15	6.90	Very Satisfactory
Kindergarteners' Exposed to Non-Story Telling Aloud Strategy	40	82.77	6.29	Satisfactory

Legend: 90-100, Outstanding; 85-89, Very Satisfactory; 80-84, Satisfactory; 75-79, Fairly Satisfactory; Below 75, Did Not Meet Expectations (Failed)

Table 4 presents level of academic performance of the kindergarten learners exposed to storytelling aloud and non-storytelling aloud strategy. As seen in the table, kindergarteners exposed to storytelling aloud strategy obtained a mean score of 85.15 interpreted as very satisfactory, while kindergarteners exposed to non-story telling aloud strategy managed only a mean score of 82.77 interpreted as satisfactory.

The data revealed that kindergarteners exposed to storytelling aloud strategy have better performance or grades in reading comprehension as compared to those exposed to non-storytelling aloud strategy. By enabling learners to understand stories and story elements and to unearth key dialogue, storytelling can help students develop their writing skills (Satriani, 2019). Learning to tell and write excellent stories is a powerful language learning application for students to improve their vocabulary and grammar (Nicholas et al., 2011).

Additionally, narrative teaches students to use their imaginations more (Wright, 1995). The narrative nature of picture books enables viewers or readers to think about how aesthetic components serve as a form of visual communication. The illustrator uses gesture, performance, and movement to show how one character interacts with others or advances that character's goals in the story (Pahl & Rowsell, 2012). Children's creativity can be developed through reading aloud stories.

Even though there has been a lot of research on employing storytelling in the classroom, there are still several studies that examine the advantages and difficulties of doing so. Our research aims to fill this gap by gathering opinions from students, teachers, and education experts regarding storytelling in the classroom and its effect on student enrolment.

This finding supports the claims of (ChazanPREVIEW 3 Cohen, & Kisker, 2013). Emergent literacy is thought to be particularly important during the years before kindergarten. Students' developmental stage and skill set when they first enter a formal educational setting are complex reflections of their environment, both within and outside the home. The cornerstone of all learning, which has been defined as language and literacy, is significantly impacted by these experiences. The growth and skill set that pupils start school with are enhanced by formal education (Crim et al., 2008).

According to research, children who lack the basic reading skills when they start kindergarten tend to lag their peers, and their difficulties with literacy in elementary school are indicators of their future difficulties with literacy in both school and in adulthood.

According to (Baillet, Repper, Murphy, Piasta, & Zettler-Greeley, 2011; Froiland, Powell, Diamond, & Claire Son, 2013; Gettinger & Stoiber, 2012) Froiland, Powell, Diamond, & Claire Son, 2013. There is an increasing sense of urgency to intervene for "at-risk students" before entering kindergarten as accountability levels rise. President Johnson launched Head Start as a program to fight the

war on poverty. Its objective was to raise the possibility that children living in poverty would be prepared for school.

Giving poor children access to a high-quality preschool education before they enter kindergarten is one method being utilized to address the achievement gap. Closing the gap before children enter school is less expensive than doing so once they are school-age (Bailet et al., 2011; Lee, Zhai, Brooks-Gunn, & Han, 2014).

Problem 5. Is there a significant difference in the academic performance of kindergarten learners exposed to storytelling aloud and non-storytelling aloud strategy?

Table 5. Results of T-test Analysis for the significant difference in the level of academic performance between the pupils exposed to the storytelling aloud strategy and non-storytelling Aloud Strategy

<i>Group</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Storytelling Aloud Strategy	40	85.15	6.90			
Non-Story Telling Aloud Strategy	40	82.77	6.29	1.61	.112	Not Significant

Table 5 presents the Results of T-test Analysis for the significant difference in academic performance of kindergarten learners exposed to storytelling aloud and non-storytelling aloud strategy. As depicted in the Table, kindergarteners exposed to Storytelling aloud strategy has obtained a higher mean score of 85.15 as compared to those kindergarteners exposed to non-story telling aloud strategy who obtained a mean score of 82.77. However, the probability value is .112 which is greater than the alpha value of .05 which indicates that the two mean scores are statistically the same or there is no significant difference between the two mean scores.

This means that as far as the over-all grades of the kindergarteners' is concerned, both strategies used are equally effective in improving the reading comprehension of the kindergarteners. The correlations between each reading style with comprehension, however, are erratic, according to prior research.

Further research is therefore required to determine whether type of reading technique makes a greater contribution to reading comprehension. Uncertainty exists regarding the degree of link between reading comprehension and strategy when reading stages and cognitive development are considered. To ascertain the relationship between each reading technique and reading comprehension, the current study uses a meta-analytic approach.

Additionally, it examines how age and script variations affect the relationship between each reading method and reading comprehension. This study expanded the existing literature on the impact of the four categories of reading strategy on reading comprehension through the meta-analytic method, exploring the correlation between four reading strategies and reading comprehension in different grade groups and languages to clarify the impact of the reading stage and the effects of cognitive developmental relations on the association between the four categories of reading strategy and reading comprehension. Garcia and Cain (2014) show that before the master's degree learning phase, readers' procedural knowledge of comprehension develops more quickly.

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According to the study, despite the numerous literature reviews that have been done (e.g., Evans & Jones, 2007; Hland et al.; Lennox, 2013; Saracho & Spodek, 2007), there is still a need for more studies that are based on fresh data. Preschool teachers have noted in numerous international studies that many kids struggle with speech and language development and need guidance (e.g., Wilson, Citation2011).

There is a great need for various communication modes. Preschool, which encompasses both childcare and kindergarten, is crucial for a child's growth. The inclusive preschool is open to all children, both typical and atypical, and its motto is "a (pre)school for all" in Sweden. The main goal of this article is to determine whether and how storytelling and reading aloud to children might improve their communication skills, as has been shown in numerous international research.

Everyone must deal with the term "false news" (Hessan & Bernoff, 2019), and literacy abilities need to be emphasized. Current investigation suggests that the reading standards for our pupils' skills far outweigh the conventional ability to find information, then condense it and pinpoint the core notion (2012) Murnane, Sawhill, and Snow.

Additionally, to learn the fundamentals of classical reading, children need to be able to evaluate, analyze, and synthesize concepts from a text between various texts. They must also be capable of spot prejudice, omitted points of view, and false slants" and economic factors (Jazyanka, 2017). What we know is based on reading theory taught in the classroom. regarding how students read. student application methods Using projects to test one's reading abilities could reveal the efficiency of one's abilities. According to Manarin et al. (2015), there are four reading traits that go beyond symbol decoding; according to the argument, regardless of its goal, reading calls for four basic abilities: understanding, analyzing, interpreting, and assessment.

Conclusion

Based on the results presented, the following conclusions are drawn: The storytelling aloud strategy was effective in helping kindergarteners improve their reading comprehension. The non-storytelling aloud strategy is a promising intervention for improving the reading comprehension skills of kindergarteners. Storytelling strategy has an impact on kindergarten learners' reading comprehension. Academic performance or grades are slightly higher for students exposed to storytelling strategy compared to those non-exposed to storytelling group. The two groups are very similar in their ability to achieve good grades.

Based on the findings and conclusions formulated, the researcher came up with the following recommendations: Storytelling strategy could be part of the classroom routine of all kindergarten learners who would be allowed to story read aloud regularly. Other non-storytelling strategies, such as games, could be utilized by kindergarten teachers. The school administration could provide more reading material to be used in the classroom setting and have the teacher training make the teacher's reading material for the benefit of the learners. Storytelling could be implemented to teach in all subjects or any subject used to improve the learner's academic performance across learning domains. The school could provide another strategy aside from storytelling that could be implemented to gain understanding, and teachers could allow their learners to be exposed to other extra-curricular activities in Arts, Music, or all parts of the domain not limited to storytelling.

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